

INTRODUCTION

- *Welcome*
- *Participant information sheet*
- *GDPR and consent → signature!*
- *Turn on recorder!*

WARM UP AND PRE-Q QUESTIONS

Topic	Prompt & potential follow-up questions	Potential aspects of interest
Farm	<p>Could you briefly introduce your farm to me?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How large is your farm? Which livestock do you hold? • What are the main crops you grow? • How do you mainly sell your produce? • To what extent would you say your farm is typical for this area here? • Who is involved in farm decisions? 	<p>Farm type Family farm Main crops Direct marketing / wholesale /... Specificities of the farm</p>
Farmer	<p>Could you tell me about your role on the farm?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How did you become a farmer on this farm? • How long have you been farming this farm? • What is your agricultural education? 	<p>Decision making Farming experience Ag education</p>
Farming conditions	<p>Could you tell me some basic information about the farming conditions on your farm?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How good is your soil? • To what extent is there sloping land on your farm? • What are the weather challenges? Have they changed in the past? • How consolidated/scattered is your land? 	<p>Soil productivity Topography Climatic conditions climate change Farmland fragmentation</p>
Soil management	<p>Could you briefly describe your soil management strategy on your cropland to me?</p> <p>Have you made any changes in your soil management during your time as a farmer on this farm?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Why? Were there any specific reasons? • Are any of your practices subsidized? 	<p>Adaptation to climate change Specific events Subsidy programs</p>

Q METHODOLOGY: SORTING

We now have a little exercise for you. We brought some cards with us that have statements on them that concern your work with the soil. These are about your **own opinion** and what you **personally** think is important, so there is **no “right” or “wrong”**, just your judgement about **your own situation**.

We are asking you to do the following:

- **Read** each card (*offer to read it out aloud to farmers if trouble reading!*)
- For each card, decide “from your guts” (i.e., **spontaneously**) whether you **agree**, **disagree**, or are **indifferent** about the statement
- Create **three piles** for these agree – disagree – indifferent cards

Next

- Take only the “**agree**” **pile** and find those statements you agree with the **very most**, i.e., that are most important to you, and sort them into the prepared grid on the **far-right** side
- Find those statements you agree with the **next** most and sort them next to the most important ones, etc.

Next

- Do the same with the “**disagree**” **pile** of cards and identify those you disagree with **most** and sort them on the **far-left** side of the grid
- Finish by sorting the “**indifferent**” statements in the **middle** of the grid.

Finally

- Take a look at the final sorting: does this seem meaningful to you? Make **changes** if necessary.

Q METHODOLOGY: REFLECTION

- Now when we consider the cards here on the far right, can you explain to me, **how did you decide to put these cards there?**
- When you **first read this** statement, what came to your mind? What does [**topic on card**] **mean** to you?
- ...same for far left...

- Which of the cards were **most difficult** for you to put into the grid? **Why** was that?
- To what extent do you feel like we **messed out on something** important? Is there any statement you think we should have included in addition?
- What did you think about when you read “**work with your soil**”? Which activities, aspects, considerations, feelings?

GOOD FARMER

Now I would like to ask you a few things concerning how you consider yourself and other farmers. Therefore, I would like to ask you some questions regarding what it might mean to be a "good" farmer from your perspective. That is, someone who manages their farm in a good and exemplary way according to you.

Topic	Prompt & follow-up questions
Good farmer	How would you describe a good farmer from your region ? How could you see it on his/her fields and farms? What do you mean by XY (e.g., "tidy")?
Bad farmer	How would you describe a bad farmer from your region ? How could you see it on his/her fields and farms?
Changes	Has your opinion concerning what a good farmer is, changed since you began as a farmer? If yes, how ?

QUESTIONNAIRE AND DEBRIEFING

Ask to fill out **form with demographics / general information**

Thank you, I think this is all the information we need! Thanks again for taking the time!

Issues you may want to mention or discuss in addition here:

- Other interview partner suggestions?
- Stakeholder workshops with results presentation next winter: interested in joining?
- Interested in receiving country-specific results of the project (may take some months)?
- Reaffirm that participants can always contact you with questions or concerns.

